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FABRICATION AND COMPRESSIVE BEHAVIORS OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITE SANDWICH STRUCTURES WITH CURVED-CREASE FOLDCORE

Yuntong Du*, Jian Xiong

Center for Composite Materials and Structures, Harbin Institute of Technology, Harbin, P. R. China

duyuntong@hit.edu.cn, yuntong1992@163.com

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1. Research background

Lighter and stronger structures have attracted significant interest in applications including aerospace, marine, automotive. Composite sandwich structures attract increasing attentions.

Foldcore is obtained by origami

Sebastien J.P. Callens, Amir A. Zadpoor. *Materials Today*, 2017.

Compared to honeycomb, foldcores provide open channels for ventilation and multifunctional designs.

Compared to corrugated cores, foldcores alleviate the severe anisotropy of the in-plane mechanical properties.

1. Research background

Razdaibedin A A , Khaliulin V I . Russian Aeronautics, 2015.

HaHnel F , Wolf K , Hauffe A , et al. CEAS Aeronautical Journal, 2011.

Sandwich curved shells, sandwich cylindrical shells and wedge-shaped folded sandwich cores could be folded by origami method.

- The stress concentration in the crease lines of foldcores should be avoided.

Stress S11 contours of folded walls under a compressive strain of 0.2%, (a) 0ply, (b) 90ply, (c) 45ply and (d) -45ply.

Sun Y, Li Y. Composites Science and Technology, 2017, 150: 95-101.

- The out-of-plane compressive strength of chevron foldcore is much lower than that of honeycomb

Gattas J M , You Z . International Journal of Solids and Structures, 2015, 53:80-91.

- The fabrication quality of composite foldcores should be improved.

2. Design of composite curved-crease origami foldcore sandwich structures

Independent geometric parameters $h \quad l \quad \beta \quad \theta \quad t$

Relative density

$$\rho_{Vr} = \frac{t}{h} \sqrt{1 + \frac{\tan^2 \beta}{\sin^2 \theta}} \quad \rho_{Sr} = \frac{t}{h \sin 2\theta} \int_0^{\pi-2\theta} \sqrt{\tan^2 \beta + \cos^2 \varphi} d\varphi$$

Straight lines are changed into circular arcs

There is no much difference between chevron foldcore and curved-crease foldcore in terms of weight

3. Analytical models of curved-crease foldcore subjected to out-of-plane compression

$$E_z = \begin{cases} \frac{E_s t \sin^3 \beta \tan \beta}{(h + w \tan \beta) \sin 2\theta} \int_0^{\pi-2\theta} \sqrt{\sin^2 \beta + \cos^2 \varphi \cos^2 \beta} d\varphi, & \frac{\pi}{4} \leq \theta < \frac{\pi}{2} \\ \frac{E_s t \sin^3 \beta \tan \beta}{h + w \tan \beta}, & \theta = \frac{\pi}{2} \end{cases}$$

$$\sigma_{zc} = \begin{cases} \frac{t \sin \beta \tan \beta \sigma_f}{(h + w \tan \beta) \sin 2\theta} \int_0^{\pi-2\theta} \sqrt{\sin^2 \beta + \cos^2 \varphi \cos^2 \beta} d\varphi, & \frac{\pi}{4} \leq \theta < \frac{\pi}{2} \\ \frac{t \sin \beta \tan \beta}{h + w \tan \beta} \sigma_f, & \theta = \frac{\pi}{2} \end{cases}$$

$$\sigma_{cr} = k_c \sigma_E$$

Based on
Stowell
theory

$$\sigma_E = \frac{\pi^2 E_s}{12(1-\nu^2)} \left(\frac{t}{b}\right)^2$$

$$k_c = 2 \left(1 + \sqrt{1 + \frac{3(1-\nu^2)}{\pi^4} \frac{b^4}{R^2 t^2}} \right)$$

Buckling strength

$$\sigma_{zcr} = \frac{\pi^2 E_s t^3 \sin \beta \tan \beta}{6(1-\nu^2)(h + w \tan \beta) b l \sin \theta} \left(1 + \sqrt{1 + \frac{3(1-\nu^2)}{\pi^4} \frac{b^4}{R^2 t^2}} \right)$$

4. Experiments and finite element analysis of curved-crease foldcore

Fabrication Process

Hot press molding method

Specimen image

4. Experiments and finite element analysis of curved-crease foldcore

Buckling strength of curved-crease foldcore is much higher than that of chevron foldcore.

As the relative density increase, the failure mode of curved-crease foldcore changes from buckling to fracture.

4. Experiments and finite element analysis of curved-crease foldcore

Modified Ashby map

Carbon fiber reinforced curved-crease origami foldcores outperform many cellular materials such as GFRP corrugated core, CFRP 3D corrugate core, and the foldcores made of aluminum, polymers and aramid fiber composites.

Although fabricated by carbon fiber composites with lower mechanical properties, the curved-crease origami foldcores developed in this paper still have similar compressive strength with other foldcores made of carbon fiber composites

5. Conclusions

- A curved-crease foldcore is designed by a transformation of chevron foldcore. And this process does not bring much weight increasing.
- A mold is designed to fabricate carbon fiber reinforced foldcore by hot press molding method. Fiber breakage is not observed during the fabrication process owing to the slow change of fiber along the curved walls. Failures do not happen in the crease lines when subjecting to loads.
- The curved-crease origami foldcores have a better antibuckling capacity than the chevron origami foldcores.